

Social Media Marketing

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Abstract

The scope of this thesis is to show the importance of usage of social media as a tool for marketing and expanding the business. Social media is a tool with which internet users build a smooth relationship between people around the world. A wide range of people are internet users and also the users of social media. As people spend their time on social media during their leisure time, this comfort psychology of the consumers must be utilized by the business entrepreneurs as an effective marketing strategy for the advertisement of their products and promoting their sales. A small business started by a single person can emerge out as a large company with the help of social media. The main aim of social media for marketing is to create publicity for their products and promote their sales.

Introduction

In this fast-moving world, there is tremendous growth in technologies. People try to update them towards the developed technologies. According to statistics, in 2019, it is estimated that there will be around 2.77 billion social media users around the globe, up from 2.46 billion in 2017. Villages and small towns are adapting to the digital revolution. About two-thirds of the global internet users access the internet to meet their daily entertainment and communication. India is perhaps the second largest country in the world for the usage of the internet. One of the primary usages of the internet is among the internet users is the usage of social media. Most of the companies have started to allocate funds for advertising in social media for grabbing the opportunities for branding and interaction. The key motivating factor for undertaking the research is the growing population of internet users. The social media user refers to a person who has a minimum of one social media account. Facebook, WhatsApp, youtube, Instagram, Twitter, LinkedIn, etc. are the few examples of social media in which facebook tops in the list of the most used social media followed by youtube and WhatsApp.

Social Media

Social Media, as defined by Wikipedia, "Social media are computer-mediated technologies that allow the creating and sharing of information, ideas, career interests and other forms of expression via virtual communities and networks." Standard features on various social media platforms are:

- Social media are web 2.0 interactive applications run by the Internet.
- The key to each social media platform is content generated by its users; it may be photos, videos, text comments, or any other online communication.
- Each user creates their profile on different social media websites that were taken care of by social media organizations.

Marketing

Dictionary.com defines marketing as “the action or business of promoting and selling products or services, including market research and advertising.”

Marketing Research

The term “Research” refers to investigating systematically to identify innovative ideas. Marketing means promoting the products, increasing sales, generating revenue and enjoying profits. Thus, marketing research requires information to analyze the results and interpret the findings.

Social Media Marketing

Marketing with the help of social media is called social media marketing. The contents are created and shared on social media networks to achieve the target of the business. The contents can be in the form of images, videos and includes other methods of sharing them. Advertising is also done on paid social media platforms for better response.

Digital Marketing

Digital marketing encompasses all marketing efforts that use an electronic device or the internet. Businesses leverage digital channels such as search engines, social media, email, and other websites to connect with current and prospective customers to promote their sales and growth of the business.

Objectives

- To promote the sales of small scale businesses with less or no investment.
- To promote work-life balance.
- To earn profits with the help of social media marketing strategies.

Many people are interested in starting a new business. The barrier of starting a new business is no sufficient funds as the capital. But social media can be utilized as a platform for such people with no investment and also earn valuable profits for their sales.

Many people want to balance both their work and life. The standard of living, income, etc. plays a vital role in the choice of work. Social media marketing is part of digital marketing. In case, the person has no computer with him, a mobile phone with an internet connection is enough to promote their sales in social media.

The quality and the price of the products determine the reputation of the business carried out and will result in progressive growth. It helps the B2B chain function most interactively.

Procedure

- Open a social media account in any social media.
- Invite followers to your account.
- The number of followers, the more will be the promotions for sales.
- Start posting your products and fix reasonable rates for those products.

- The description contains the quality, time of delivery, cost of the products, etc.,
- The consumers will get all the necessary information about the products.
- The description also contains personal contacts such as mobile number, mail id, etc.

Research Methodology

The sample size calculated for the study was 200 consumers with the help of social media. The primary information was collected with the help of a well-structured questionnaire to different online users in Tamilnadu through Email, Facebook, and Whatsapp. Participants were further asked to forward the link and draft to other contacts to help me in data collection. The sample consists of young people. Their psychology gives a positive review to the online market. Most of the answers were in favor of social media marketing as it saves time and energy for the consumers. 24*7 availability of the products boosts the people to purchase more conveniently. The satisfaction of consumers is the key factor in social media marketing. The people with the age group of 20- 35 are the participants in the survey as the young minds purchase more of products both for their children and their grandparents.

Interpretation

1. Whether People Prefer Online or Offline Shopping?

70% of the people in the survey prefer online shopping, and only 30% prefer offline shopping. The reason behind the majority of the vote to online shopping is the time-saving process.

Chart 1. People prefer online shopping or offline shopping

2. Which is the Frequently Used Social Media in Recent Times?

Facebook tops with 40% usage, followed by YouTube with 30% and Whatsapp with 25% of usage. The other social media such as Instagram, Twitter, etc., were also used in minimum numbers.

Chart 2. Frequently used social media

3. Whether Men Prefer Online Shopping More or Women?

Women considerably prefer online shopping more because they prefer to buy their requirements from home with their savings. Men are free to reach out to places than women. So comparatively women buy more online products. The choice is more in online shopping.

Chart 3. Men prefer online shopping more or Women

4. Reach of Advertising in Social Media

The people with the age group of 20-25 prefer more online shopping as their requirements are more to adapt to recent trends. The people of 25-30 relatively show a lesser preference for online shopping. The 30-35 aged people prefer offline shopping due to their traditional way of purchasing through direct contact and are unaware of the benefits of online shopping.

Chart 4. Reach of advertising in social media

Feedback From Customers

- Feedback from our customers will help us to know their tastes and preferences.
- It will help us to bring products according to their wish and gain a valuable profit.
- Analyzing market trends is only from the feedback.

At the End of the First Year

- 4 Products x 50 Rs profit = Rs 200 per day.
- Rs 200 x 30 days= Rs 6000 per month.
- Rs 6000 x 12 months= Rs 72000 per annum.

Assuming a person has sold four products daily through social media marketing without investment, then his yearly profit will Rs 72000. A business with no investment to a valuable amount at the end of the first year is a great motivation to start a business from homes.

Findings and Suggestions

- The above result of the survey proves that social media provides a platform to start and expand our business. All age groups prefer online shopping, and it is the easiest way to promote with less or no investment.
- People being in their homes can start a business with their small savings initially and develop their business from prospective profits.
- The time and energy for both the buyers and sellers will be less and expands the number of consumers for the products.

Conclusion

In recent times, people want to work independently and earn for their own life. Social media marketing is one of the mobile marketing strategies which are used to cover a wide range of consumers. In short, the offline market is like the tiger chasing its prey. But the online market is like a spider that captures its prey with the help of the web. The more promotional ideas, the more will be the sales.

Thus we conclude that a successful business needs proper plans. So plan today, start your own business, in your style considering our above thesis and gain more profit from online trading.